

was heated (150-60°, 3 h), then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water (10 ml). The solution was kept at room temperature (12 h), diluted with water (30 ml) and extracted thrice with ether (20 ml). The combined ether extract was washed twice with saturated sodium bicarbonate (15 ml) and water (20 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of solvent furnished **III** (0.510 g), which was chromatographed on silica gel. The column was eluted with petroleum ether as eluent and the product obtained was identical with that obtained by isobutyryl chloride-pyridine method on **II**.

Acknowledgement

We thank the C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi for research fellowships (D.G.D. and R.K.R.) and Prof. M. H. Jagdale for encouragement.

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Some New Thiosemicarbazones and 1,3,4-Thiazolinylnyls as Potential Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents

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Manuscript received 4 June 1982, accepted 30 May 1983

THE tuberculostatic activity of thiosemicarbazones and related compounds was first observed by Domagk *et al*¹. Thiosemicarbazides and their derivatives possess various biological activities²⁻⁵ and are extensively used in medicine especially in the treatment of tuberculosis. Antimicrobial and antitumor activity are also shown by thiosemicarbazones^{6,7}.

Cyclization of thiosemicarbazides gives various heterocyclic systems depending on the reagent and other conditions of cyclization. 4-Substituted thiosemicarbazides on diazotisation gives thiazolines⁸.

The structure of the reported compounds have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and infrared spectra. All the compounds have been synthesised according to the following scheme.

Synthesis and screening of 4,4'-di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (**I**) shows as tuberculostatic and antibacterial activity. 4,4'-Bis (5-arylimino-substituted benzaldehyde)-1,3,4-thiadiazolinylnyl-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl shows antibacterial activity.

Following bands are observed in ir spectra 1150 cm⁻¹ (>C=S), 1310 cm⁻¹ (>C=N) and 3450 cm⁻¹ (>NH). The band due to >C=N stretching is lost on thiadiazolinylnyl formation and strong tertiary amide stretch is observed around 1320cm⁻¹ and secondary amine shifts towards higher wave length at 3460 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

The ir spectra were recorded in Unicam SP-1025 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase.

4,4'-Di-(3-thiosemicarbazide)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl: To *o*-tolidine (0.01 mol) dissolved in ammonia (0.02 mol), carbon disulfide (0.02 mol) added and cooled below 30°. Ethanol (95%, 30 ml) was added and stirred for 30 min, contents allowed to stand for 2 h at room temperature. A solution of sodium chloroacetate (0.02 mol) was added followed by hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol, 50%), warmed and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to half its volume and allowed to stand overnight, when crystals of thiosemicarbazides separated, filtered washed with water, dried, recrystallised from ethanol (95%), yield 78%, m.p. 185°.

4,4'-Di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (I): 4,4'-Di-(3-thiosemicarbazide)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (95%, 50 ml) for 2 h, contents allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. and activity recorded in Table 1.

4,4'-Di-(5-arylimino-2-substituted benzaldehyde)-1,3,4-thiadiazolinylnyl-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (II): 4,4'-Di-(substituted benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (95%) and NaOH solution with a little water (5 ml). The mixture was heated on waterbath until

TABLE 1—THIOSEMICARBAZONES OF THE TYPE I

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Reqd.)	
				N	S
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S	226	15.48 (15.67)	12.09 (11.94)
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	231	14.92 (14.78)	11.42 (11.26)
3.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	222	11.34 (11.57)	8.68 (8.81)
4.	-3,5.di.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	207	9.75 (9.50)	7.39 (7.23)
5.	-2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂	235	14.62 (13.88)	10.76 (10.57)
6.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	241	14.26 (14.09)	10.89 (10.73)
7.	-C ₇ H ₇ O	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	150	16.46 (16.21)	12.49 (12.35)
8.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	250	17.62 (17.89)	10.38 (10.22)
9.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	210	17.64 (17.89)	10.46 (10.22)
10.	-CH-CH.C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	246	16.11 (15.90)	11.02 (10.88)
11.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	242	13.42 (13.37)	10.41 (10.19)
12.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	125	14.92 (14.78)	11.49 (11.26)
13.	-3.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	189	14.99 (14.78)	11.51 (11.26)
14.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	218	15.05 (14.89)	11.56 (11.34)
15.	-4.N(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ S ₂	216	18.28 (18.00)	10.49 (10.28)

TABLE 2—THIADIAZOLINYL OF TYPE II

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Reqd.)	
				N	S
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	215	15.92 (15.78)	12.26 (12.03)
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	140	15.01 (14.89)	11.58 (11.34)
3.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	190	11.78 (11.63)	8.99 (8.86)
4.	-3,5.di.Br.2.OH.-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₈ Br ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	170	9.79 (9.54)	7.49 (7.27)
5.	-2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂	190	14.16 (13.97)	10.79 (10.64)
6.	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	174	14.37 (14.18)	11.06 (10.92)
7.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	183	8.19 (8.00)	10.51 (10.28)
8.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	201	18.23 (18.00)	10.53 (10.28)
9.	-C ₇ H ₇ O	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	160	16.39 (16.21)	12.54 (12.35)
10.	-CH-CH.C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	192	14.21 (14.38)	11.11 (10.95)
11.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	199	14.25 (14.00)	10.89 (10.66)
12.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	152	15.02 (14.89)	11.53 (11.34)
13.	-3.OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	179	15.04 (14.89)	11.23 (11.34)
14.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	181	14.79 (15.00)	11.62 (11.42)
15.	-4.N(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	205	18.37 (18.18)	10.59 (10.38)

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY OF TYPE I AND II

Sl. No.	R	Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 μ g conc/disk		Mycobact. antituberculosis activity ($H_{37} R_v$)	Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 μ g conc/disk	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	-	-	+	-	-
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
3.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	+	-	+	+	-
4.	-3,5-di-Bromo-2-OH. -C ₆ H ₃	++	+	+	++	+
5.	-2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	-	-	-	-	-
6.	-C ₄ H ₉ O	-	-	+	-	-
7.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	++	+	+	+	+
8.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	-	-
9.	-CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	+	+	+	+	+
10.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	++	+	+	++	+
11.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
12.	-3.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-	-	+	-	-
13.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
14.	-4.N(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
15.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-

Columns 3 to 5 indicate activity of thiosemicarbazones.

Columns 6 and 7 indicate activity of thiadiazolinylns.

+ = zone diameter less than 20 mm ; ++ = zone diameter more than 20 mm ; - = no inhibition.

aqueous potassium ferricyanide solution (5%) added dropwise with shaking ceased further precipitation. The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water to remove potassium ferricyanide and crystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. recorded in Table 2.

Antitubercular activity: *In vitro* antitubercular activity of the hitherto synthesised thiosemicarbazone derivatives was studied against $H_{37} R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 μ g/ml and the retardation of the growth rate was recorded upto 6 weeks at 37° (Table 3).

Antibacterial activity: The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by N-agar pour plate method in dimethylformamide and they were found to be active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentration (Table 3).

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Bhavnagar University for J.R.Fs (N.C.D., H.K.S and B.R.P.) and also to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amersgadh, for screening the samples.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) and Stepwise Formation Constants of Its Complexes with N-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide and N-(4-Methyl-phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide

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Manuscript received 5 January 1981, revised 19 August 1983,
accepted 25 March 1984

THE spectrophotometric determination of palladium are numerous but still there are very few selective reagents where the other platinum group metals do not interfere. It was suggested¹⁻³ that the substituted dithio-oxamides are very sensitive reagents for trace determination of palladium. It was found^{4,5} that reagents containing the nitroso-phenylamine group (e.g. *p*-nitrosodiphenyl aniline) are one of the most sensitive reagents for palladium. The other important sensitive and selective reagents reported are 2-aldehyde 2-quinolylylhydrazones⁶, 1-(2-carboxy-4-sulfonato phenyl) 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl triazine⁷, promethazine hydrochloride⁸, N,N' bis-(3-dimethyl-aminopropyl) dithio-oxamide⁹, phenyl α -pyridyl ketoxime¹⁰, and 1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-naphthol¹¹. The review¹² reported several organic reagents for photometric determination of palladium and they are mainly organic acids, dyes, heterocyclic bases, triazines, oximes and sulphur bearing ligands.

The present investigation attempts to find some chromogenic reagents for palladium with sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms. Effect on sensitivity with change of functional groups were also investigated. The method was extended to the